

THE EFFECT OF HYDROGEN-ION CONCENTRATION ON THE TIME OF SETTING OF THORIUM PHOSPHATE GEL-FORMING MIXTURES

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The investigation deals with the determination of the effect of the H-ion concentration on the time of setting. The time of setting of thorium phosphate gel-forming mixtures in all cases has been found at first to increase, then decrease and reach a minimum, followed by a rise, as the p_H of the mixture is continuously decreased. The minimum time of setting takes place at lower and lower p_H as the concentration of phosphoric acid in the mixture is decreased. There is a linear relation between the amounts of phosphoric and hydrochloric acids corresponding to the minimum time of setting. p_H and $\log t$ curves are not straight lines as observed by Hurd and co-workers in the case of silicic acid gel-forming mixtures.

The effect of the addition of ethyl alcohol on the time of setting of gel-forming mixtures of different p_H (those which set in minimum time and others which set before and after the minimum time) is of the same nature. There is an increase in the time of setting, which reaches a maximum value and then falls as the amount of alcohol in the mixture is increased; the maximum has the lowest value for mixtures of p_H corresponding to the minimum time of setting.

The mixtures set to a gel only when their p_H values are less than 1.7; beyond this value a precipitate and not a gel is formed. No change in the p_H of the mixtures takes place either on standing or on the addition of different amounts of alcohol.

The effect of hydrogen-ion concentration on the time of setting of gels has been studied most extensively in the case of gels of silicic acid. This effect was first pointed out by Holmes (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1918, 22, 570) who observed that silicic acid gels containing a very slight excess of OH-ions set in the shortest time and the time of setting rapidly increased with an increase in the H-ion concentration. He has also observed that there is a concentration of H-ion which delays the time of setting indefinitely and beyond this concentration the time of setting of the gel again becomes measurable and rapidly decreases to an immediate set. In the latter case he concludes that it is the dehydrating influence of the non-ionised molecules of acid which controls the time of setting. Prasad and Hattiangadi (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 893) have also observed that the time of setting is minimum when the p_H of the silicic acid gel-forming mixture is slightly higher than 7 and it is considerably increased in moderately acidic or highly alkaline mixtures. Ray and Ganguli (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1930, 34, 352) found that for each concentration of the alkali silicate solution there was a limiting range of p_H value between which gel-formation took place.

Recently considerable amount of systematic work on the effect of p_H on the time of setting of silicic acid gel-forming mixtures has been done by Hurd and co-workers. Hurd and Carver (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1933, 37, 321) found that an increase in the p_H of the silicic acid gel-forming mixture decreased the time of setting. Hurd, Raymond and Miller (*ibid.*, 1934, 38, 668) have found that with gel-forming mixtures made up of sodium silicate and hydrochloric acid and having p_H 4.2 to 5.5 and those made up of sodium silicate and acetic acid and having p_H 4.14 to 6.0, the time of setting appears to be a linear function of the H-ion concentration. Hurd and Paton (*ibid.*, 1940, 44, 57) have confirmed in a remarkable manner, the specific effect of H-ion concentration on the time of setting of silicic acid gels. On adding the same amount of extra acetic acid to the same silicic acid gel-forming mixture at different intervals from the commencement of the formation of the gel, they have shown that the setting of the gel proceeds at the same rate as without the addition of the extra acid, for the time before the acid is added, and subsequently at the rate followed in the presence of the extra acid added at the commencement of the setting.

Some observations on the effect of H-ion concentration on the time of setting are available in the case of other gels also. Freundlich and Söllner (*Kolloid Z.*, 1928, 44, 309; 48, 348) found that the time of setting of iron hydroxide gel increased from 82 seconds to 9000 seconds when the p_H of the gel-forming system was changed from 3.86 to 3.17. Prasad, Mehta and Parmar (*Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1936, 3A, 107) have found that the time of setting of mixtures giving rise to thorium phosphate gels is increased with the addition of sodium hydroxide of increasing concentration, while with the addition of increasing amounts of hydrochloric and nitric acids, the time of setting first diminished, reached a minimum and then increased and was again abruptly followed by a second minimum. With sulphuric acid there is only one minimum. Prasad and Desai (*J. Univ. Bom.* 1938, 7, 132) have found that with the addition of increasing amounts of hydrochloric acid to thorium molybdate gel-forming mixtures, the time of setting first decreases, reaches a minimum and then increases and again decreases to a second minimum, followed by a rapid rise. Desai (unpublished work) found that the time of setting of thorium arsenate gel-forming mixtures first decreased, reached a minimum, and then increased as the quantity of hydrochloric acid in the mixture was increased. On plotting the logarithm of the time of setting against the logarithm of the concentration of hydrochloric acid, he found that the curves were made up of two intersecting straight lines.

In the present investigation the hydrogen ion concentration and the time of setting of thorium phosphate gel-forming mixtures containing various amounts of HCl have been studied systematically with a view to throwing light on the peculiar behaviour of acids observed by previous workers.

EXPERIMENTAL

Hurd and Letteron's method (*J. Phys. Chem.* 1932, 36, 604) was used in the present investigation for the measurement of the time of setting. The apparatus was placed in a thermostat kept at 35 ± 0.02 . The original device of Hurd and Letteron was improved upon by fixing a handle to the gear arrangement so that the supporting rod could be turned from without, thus obviating the necessity of opening the glass door of the thermostat. Another modification made was the fixing of a cross wire in front of the horizontal rod so that the latter could be brought back to its original position with reference to the former if the gel did not set.

Preparation of Solutions.—Thorium nitrate (6%) solution was prepared from Kahlbaum's pure thorium nitrate. The exact concentration of the solution was determined gravimetrically. The thoria content was found to be 2.800%, the theoretical amount being 2.875% for an $N/10$ solution. Phosphoric acid (approx. 2N) solution was prepared from Merck's extra pure acid by weighing. It was then standardised and made exactly 2N. Hydrochloric acid solution (2N) was prepared and used.

Procedure.—Thorium nitrate solution (5 c.c.) was measured out in each case in weighing bottles of the same dimensions. In test tubes were taken definite volumes of phosphoric acid and hydrochloric acid along with some distilled water to make up the total volume to 5 c.c. The contents of the weighing bottle were poured into the test tube and the mixture shaken for 15 seconds. It was then poured into the weighing bottle and gently inverted twice, and then allowed to set. This method of mixing was followed throughout the investigation.

It will be seen that an interval of 15 seconds has been allowed for shaking the mixture in every case. This time has not been counted in the time of setting, though strictly speaking this should be done. However, since it is the trend of results rather than the actual time of setting that is important, this has been left out. In most cases where the time of setting is of the order of

several minutes, a uniform loss of time of an interval of a few seconds cannot make much difference and can be allowed for. On the other hand, when the time of setting is only a few seconds, the time occupied in shaking can assume serious proportions. This is the case only with mixtures containing 0.7 c.c. of phosphoric acid, in which case the time of setting is extremely small. These results are, therefore, not very reliable. Their significance lies only in showing that even when the setting time is very small the same laws govern the progress of gelation.

TABLE I

Thorium nitrate = 5 c.c.

HCl.	$x=0.7^*$		$x=0.6$		$x=0.55$		$x=0.5$		$x=0.4$		$x=0.3$	
	<i>t</i> .	<i>t</i>	<i>p_n</i> .	<i>t</i> .	<i>p_n</i> .							
0.0 c.c.	12"	8'20"	0.84	14'10"	0.95	36' 0"	0.99	120'5"	1.06	—	1.19	
0.1	16"	12' 0"	0.79	16' 0"	0.91	39' 0"	0.90	—	—	—	—	
0.2	9"	13'40"	0.71	18'30"	0.89	36' 0"	0.89	—	0.83	—	0.94	
0.25	—	11'15"	0.70	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	
0.3	—	8'10"	—	—	—	33'20"	0.80	—	—	—	—	
0.4	—	9'5"	0.69	16' 0"	0.71	31' 0"	0.76	—	0.72	—	—	
0.5	13"	11'10"	0.64	14'30"	0.66	29'50"	0.73	64'45"	0.69	—	0.75	
0.6	—	—	—	13'20"	0.63	28'40"	0.72	—	0.61	—	—	
0.7	—	—	—	15' 0"	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	
0.8	—	—	—	16' 0"	0.51	26' 0"	0.60	—	0.55	—	—	
1.0	18"	19'45"	0.50	22' 0"	0.49	24'50"	0.50	55'40"	0.31	192'	0.53	
1.2	23"	—	—	—	—	30' 0"	0.39	—	—	—	—	
1.3	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	53'26"	—	185'	0.47	
1.4	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.40	—	—	
1.5	—	25' 5"	0.36	32' 0"	0.37	40'20"	0.32	56' 0"	—	—	0.38	
1.7	26"	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	
1.8	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.28	—	—	
2.0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	96'0"	0.25	177'	0.29	
2.5	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	174'	0.20	
3.0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	184'	0.15	
3.5	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	200'	0.11	
4.0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	0.05	

* The p_n values of the gel-forming mixtures containing 0.7 c.c. of phosphoric acid are very low between 0.01 and 0.10.

TABLE II

Phosphoric acid (c.c.)	...	0.60	0.55	0.50	0.40	0.30
Hydrochloric acid (c.c.)	...	0.35	0.60	1.00	1.30	1.50

After mixing the constituents, the selected glass rod was inserted in the gel-forming mixture at about an angle of 20° to the vertical. It rested against the supporting rod of the arrangement described above. A slight movement of the rod determined whether the glass rod moved from its original position. If it moved, the supporting rod was again adjusted by turning the handle to bring the glass rod back to the original position. The accuracy of these measurements was increased by repeating the observations several times, and each time disturbing the mixture as little as possible by shifting the rod only when the gel was about to set. The diameter of the glass rod used to measure the time of setting of gel-forming mixtures containing 0.40 c.c. to 0.70 c.c. of phosphoric acid was 0.094 cm., and for the mixtures containing 0.30 c.c. of phosphoric acid, it was 0.062 cm. The reason for using a rod of a smaller diameter in the latter case is that when the amount of phosphoric acid is low, the gel formed is not firm enough to support a heavier rod, thus rendering it difficult to locate the exact time of setting.

Increasing amounts of hydrochloric acid were added to several sets of the gel-forming mixtures containing the same amount of thorium nitrate and increasing amounts of phosphoric acid. The concentration of hydrochloric acid was varied from 0.2 to 3.0 c.c. of 2*N* solution and that of phosphoric acid from 0.3 to 0.7 c.c. of 2*N* solution. The total volume in every case was 10 c.c.

The H-ion concentration was measured by a p_H electrometer manufactured by Becker and Co., Ltd. The instrument was at first adjusted in accordance with the instructions supplied with it. The constituent of the various gel-forming mixtures were mixed and shaken in a test tube and then the mixture was poured into the glass dish provided for the purpose.

The results obtained are given in Table I. They represent the mean of several readings which did not differ from each other by more than 2 to 5 seconds. This accuracy was obtained only after the modifications described above were introduced in the apparatus. In the table, x represents the volume in c.c. of the phosphoric acid solution and t , the time of setting in minutes.

DISCUSSION

It will be seen from the foregoing results that with the addition of increasing amounts of hydrochloric acid, the time of setting of thorium phosphate gels first slightly increases, and then decreases and reaches a minimum and subsequently increases fairly rapidly. The slight rise in the beginning is very definite, and is not shown in the last two columns of the table, not because it does not exist, but because the time of setting of the gel-forming mixtures corresponding to this point is high and inconvenient to measure.

These results are similar to those obtained by Parmar, Mehta and Prasad (*loc. cit.*). The minimum amount of 4*N*-HCl used by these workers is 0.5 c.c. while the amounts used by the author range from 0.10 to 3.5 c.c. of 2*N*-HCl or 0.05 to 1.75 c.c. of 4*N*-HCl. This explains why Parmar, Mehta and Prasad missed the first rise observed by the author. The decrease in the time of setting after the second rise observed by Parmar, Mehta and Prasad could not be observed in this case as this occurs in the presence of 1.5 c.c. of 4*N*-HCl in the mixture containing 5.0 c.c. of thorium nitrate solution and 0.7 c.c. of the solution of phosphoric acid, while the highest amount of 2*N*-HCl used in this investigation in this mixture is 2.0 c.c.

The Minimum Point.

It will be seen from Table I that greater amounts of HCl are required to cause a gel-forming mixture to set in minimum time as the concentration of phosphoric acid in the mixture is decreased. The amounts of phosphoric acid and hydrochloric acid corresponding to the minimum time of setting are shown in Table II.

On plotting the amounts of phosphoric acid (x) and hydrochloric acid (y) from Table II a straight line (shown in Fig. 1) is obtained. This shows that effect of the two acids is complementary. On measuring the slope of the line, it is found that it can be expressed by the equation

$$y = 4 - 6x$$

$$\text{or } x = \frac{4 - y}{6}$$

This relation can be used to predict the amount of hydrochloric acid to be added to a mixture containing 5 c.c. of thorium nitrate solution and any given quantity of phosphoric acid to cause the mixture to set in the minimum time.

Effect of Phosphate-ion Concentration.—Various workers have observed that the time of setting of a gel varies with a change in the concentration of the constituents of a gel-forming mixture. In the case of gels of inorganic substances, it has been usually found that their time of setting (cf. Prakash and Dhar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 587; Parmar, Mehta and Prasad, *loc. cit.*; Prasad and Desai, *loc. cit.*) increases on decreasing the concentration of the salt carrying the acid ion of the gel-forming substance. The results obtained in this investigation are in agreement with those observed by previous workers.

mixtures against time. The linear relation between the time of setting and H-ion concentration observed by Hurd and co-workers is not observed in this case. It will be observed that the variations in the p_n values of the mixtures studied in this investigation are not great.

Effect of p_n on the Time of Setting.—The effect of p_n on the time of setting of various mixtures can be seen from Table I. On plotting p_n values against the logarithm of time of setting, curves shown in Fig. 2 for mixtures containing 0.50, 0.55 and 0.60 c.c. of phosphoric acid are obtained. These curves are practically of the same nature as the curves obtained by plotting the c.c. of HCl solution added to the gel-forming

It will be noted from Table I that the highest p_n value of the several gel-forming mixtures used in this investigation is 1.19. In order to prepare gel-forming mixtures of p_n higher than this, sodium hydroxide instead of hydrochloric acid was added to the mixture of thorium nitrate and phosphoric acid. For this purpose different volumes of 1.0 N-NaOH were added to 5.0 c.c. of 2N-phosphoric acid and the total volume was made up to 5.0 c.c. by the addition of water in the manner described before and the time of setting was measured by Fleming's method (*Z. Physik*, 1902, 41, 427). p_n values were measured immediately after mixing the solutions with the glass electrode. The results obtained are given in the following table.

TABLE III

Thorium nitrate = 5 c.c.		Phosphoric acid = 0.5 c.c.	
1.0 N-NaOH _n	Time of setting.	p_n .	Remarks.
0.0 c.c.	24 min.	0.99	Clear solution set to a transparent gel.
0.1	29	1.01	Flocculent precipitate disappears on setting
0.2	41	1.11	Do.
0.5	46	1.24	Do.
1.0	—	1.72	Precipitate formed.

It will be seen that the relationship between the p_n value and the time of setting of the above mixtures follows a regular curve within the p_n range studied. The highest point on the curve corresponds to the p_n value beyond which gel-formation does not take place; for instance when the p_n value of the gel-forming mixture is 1.7, only a precipitate is formed. This value may therefore be taken as the limiting value beyond which no gel-formation takes place.

If the results given in Table III are considered along with those given in Table I for the mixture containing 0.5 c.c. of phosphoric acid, and due allowances are made for the differences in the time of setting determined by the methods of Hurd and Fleming (*loc. cit.*) it will appear that with a regular decrease in p_n , the time of setting of this mixture undergoes a number of significant changes. It first decreases and reaches a first minimum which will probably be the mixture to which no acid or alkali is added. It then increases to a small extent and reaches a maximum value. It again decreases, and reaches a second minimum after which it again rises to a fairly high value. It will be observed that the interval between the first minimum and maximum becomes more pronounced as the amount of phosphoric acid in the gel-forming mixture is increased.

Effect of Time on the p_n of a Gel-forming Mixture.—It was observed that no change in p_n takes place during the gelation of all gels studied in this investigation. These results confirm the observations of Prasad and Desai (*J. Univ. Bom.*, 1938, 7, 132).

Effect of the Addition of Ethyl Alcohol on the Time of Setting and p_n of Gel-forming Mixtures containing different amounts of HCl.—It has been found that the effect of the addition of non-electrolytes on the time of setting of gels depends upon the nature of the gel. Prasad and Hattiangadi (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 8, 991) found that the addition of increasing amounts of alcohol to the silicic acid gel-forming mixtures decreases the time of setting in alkaline medium but if the gel-forming mixture is even slightly acidic, it is delayed considerably.

Munro and co-workers (*Canadian J. Res.*, 1937, 18, 353; 1938, 18, 390; 1939, 17, 266, 404) examined the effect of several polyhydric alcohols on the time of setting of silicic acid

gels. They found that the time of setting of alkaline gels decreased with the addition of a series of monohydric alcohols. Further they found that there was a certain p_H of the gel-forming mixtures at which the action of alcohols changed from retarding to an accelerating one.

The effect of the addition of increasing quantities of ethyl alcohol on the time of setting of certain mixtures of phosphoric and hydrochloric acids with thorium nitrate was therefore studied. These mixtures correspond to the minimum time of setting as well as before and after the minimum time of setting. The particular gel-forming mixtures on which the effect of increasing amounts of alcohol was studied were those containing (i) 0.6 c.c. phosphoric acid and 0.30, 0.25 and 0.50 c.c. of HCl and (ii) 0.5 c.c. phosphoric acid and 0.40, 1.00 and 1.20 c.c. of HCl.

The general effect of the addition of ethyl alcohol to various mixtures is similar in all cases. This can be seen from Table IV.

TABLE IV

Thorium nitrate = 5.0 c.c. Phosphoric acid = 0.6 c.c. Hydrochloric acid = 0.5 c.c. Temp. = 35°.

Alcohol (c.c.)	...	0.0	0.2	0.4	0.6	0.8	1.0	1.2	1.5	2.0
Setting time	...	11'0"	11'30"	11'40"	12'0"	13'40"	10'30"	9'30"	9'20"	9'0"
p_H	...	0.62	0.62	0.62	0.62	0.62	0.62	0.62	0.62	0.62

Thus with the addition of increasing amounts of alcohol to all the gel-forming mixtures the time of setting first increases, reaches a maximum value and then decreases, the maximum value depending upon the HCl content of the mixture. It has the lowest value for mixtures containing HCl corresponding to the minimum time of setting. This leads one to conclude that the maximum time of setting in the presence of alcohol decreases and reaches the lowest value as the amount of HCl in the gel-forming mixture reaches that corresponding to the minimum time of setting.

Although no definite information regarding the nature of the different gel-forming mixtures or set gels can be obtained from results of these experiments, it can be surmised that the structure of the gels obtained from mixtures containing HCl in amounts lower and higher than that corresponding to the minimum time of setting are essentially different. This view is substantiated from the visual observation of various gels obtained in the presence of alcohol.

It will be observed that the p_H of the gel-forming mixtures does not change with the addition of alcohol. The addition of alcohol, may, therefore, cause changes only in the rate of formation of the colloidal particles in the gel-forming mixture or in the rate of formation of ultimate particles of the gel.

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